

First Vizslas of the United States: Review of Newspaper Records

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Author Note

This paper is a continuation of previously published studies on the Vizsla history subject (Moshynska, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14852820>; Moshynska, 2020, <https://www.ancient-origins.net/history-ancient-traditions/vizsla-0013289>).

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Abstract

The Vizsla (Smooth), also known as a Hungarian Pointer, Magyar Vizsla, Magyar Pointer, or Yellow Pointer, is a beautiful, noble-looking, intelligent, and versatile breed excelling at various tasks presented to them. Vizsla may become a hunter, show prospect, competitive or non-competitive performance sport athlete, or companion. Such versatility is due to hundreds of years of selective breeding and betterment of the breed, its traits and abilities. This paper reviews the newsletter records between 1850 and 1959 that cover stories about the first Vizslas in the United States.

First Vizslas of the United States: Review of Newspaper Records

Background

Both the American Kennel Club (2022) and the Vizsla Club of America (n.d.) agree that the first Vizslas (Smooth) who set their feet on the United States' soil in 1950 were Sari and her two puppies, Shasta and Tito. However, the author came across a newspaper article mentioning a Vizsla that was published at an earlier date. The aims of this study were: 1) capture newspaper stories about early Vizslas in the United States, 2) create a reference list of the newspaper articles covering the Vizsla subject from the earliest United States records and until 1959, and 3) seek the evidence of any Vizslas possibly entering the country earlier than 1950. Thanks to the open access to information movement and the digitization efforts, millions of records became part of various digital repositories around the globe. The author of this paper reviewed the digitized newspaper records in the public repositories, Wikipedia Online Newspaper Archives, Google News Archive, and Newspapers.com. The author set the period from 1850 to 1959, and conducted the search between December 26, 2018 and August 1, 2023, and used the following keywords: Vizsla, Hungarian Pointer, Magyar Vizsla, Magyar Pointer, and Yellow Pointer. The first draft was completed and some findings presented as a part of the Master of Management in Library and Information Sciences studies (2020-2021) at the University of Southern California, Los Angeles. Some of these findings were covered in previous publications (Moshynska, 2019; Moshynska, 2020). In this paper, the author described findings in a chronologic order whenever possible.

Pre-1950 Years

Prior to 1929, any Vizsla mentionings in the newspapers appeared related to either someone's last name or business. In 1929, the American Magyar Journal published an announcement about Baba Kitroly, a retired military officer who wrote the "Magyar Vizsla" book, receiving a rejection letter to publish the book from the government of Czech Republic.

A few newspaper sources suggested that despite Hungarians disallowing their breed to leave their country, there were some exceptions to this general rule (Albany Democrat – Herald, 1950; Buffalo Evening News, 1951, 1955; King, 1959; Owens, 1958; Sharpley, 1956; The Arizona Republic, 1954). Mr. Das, who owned a Vizsla named Jutka, shared that other two puppies from Jutka's mother named Kati went to the Shah of Iran and one puppy - to the Italian King and his daughter (Buffalo Evening News, 1951). He said that years ago one Vizsla went to the Pope "when he was a papal nuncio" (Buffalo Evening News, 1955, p.37) and another one – to Aga Khan. One of Stalin's bodyguards mentioned during World War II taking a Vizsla to Russia to protect Stalin (King, 1959; The Arizona Republic, 1954). Mr. Pratt suggested that Hungarians prior to sending Vizslas outside of the country as "the gift of kings," altered the dogs' reproductive organs (Owens, 1958, p.10). However, M. L. Sharpley (1956) mentioned that an American sportsman, inspired by their hunting experience in Hungary, purchased a pair of Vizslas in 1933 from Queen Elena of Italy's Vizsla stock and believed that some modern U.S. Vizslas could be descendants of them. This would be an interesting lead to follow, though it would not be an easy task since the lack of additional information.

Leone King (1959) interviewed a Palm Beach resident Mrs. Lawrence Waterbury, who before the war in 1937, fell in love with the breed, used her connections with Hungarian authorities, and brought a female Vizsla Zsoka (or Yoka) back home with her. According to the article, this Vizsla continued to live in the United States for 14 years, with Mrs. Waterbury remembering her as "a rare combination of beauty and brains who offered protection and affection and responded to commands in three languages, Hungarian, German and English" (p. 27, para 15). King referred to Mrs. Waterbury as the one "credited with being the first Americans to own a Vizsla" (p. 27, para 13). According to Coffman (1991), there was a female Vizsla brought over by Joseph Pulitzer before 1950. Mr. Pulitzer bought her from Mike Kende. Unfortunately, the author did not find a reference to this Vizsla in the newspaper records.

A number of newsletters run a story about a British Intelligence Officer Derek Peters who in February 1943 jumped with a parachute and arrived in Hungary with the purpose of removing the St. Stephen's crown from a secure vault and giving it to the Allied Forces. After two "red-gold" coated Vizslas captured him, he fell in love with the breed that Hungarians called as "smartest in the world" dogs (King, 1959, p. 27). In 1945, Peters went to Vienna hoping to bring a Vizsla male back with him. However, both Peters and the dog were found shot to death at the border.

1950-1951

Sari and Her Two Vizsla Puppies Arrive to The U.S.

On October 7, 1950, Sari and her two puppies arrived in the United States. A Hungarian refugee family moving into New Palestine brought these three dogs to an attaché of the American Embassy in Rome, Italy (Ledger-Star, 1954). Emmett Scanlan, the U.S. State Department worker, helped Commander Frank Tallman of the United States Navy Air Force in Rome, to have these dogs sent "by diplomatic pouch" (Joiner, 1952, p. 3). It was not an easy task. Frank T. Tallman, who resided at 10 West 66th Street Terrace in Kansas City at that time, recalled getting the signed by the Minister of Agriculture in Hungary registration papers and pedigrees was even more difficult than bringing the dogs across the border (Edgar, Ledger-Star, 1954, p. 41). On July 14, 1951, a 2-year-old male Vizsla Rex Del Gelsomino arrived from Italy to join the Tallman family.

On December 3, 1950, a "sandy colored" Vizsla named Prince was reported missing in Oregon (Albany Democrat – Herald, 1950). Sadly, there were no other leads on the origins, owners, or fate of this Vizsla.

Vizsla's First Appearance in The U.S. Show Ring

On February 25, 1951, Mr. Tallman appeared with his three Vizslas in The Kansas City Star (Garich, 1951). According to this story, Mr. Tallman introduced Shara (Sari in other

references) and two little puppies Tito and Shasta in the Municipal Auditorium at the 3rd Annual Heart of America Kennel Club show (Garich, 1951).

On March 17, 1951, Tallmans reported exhibiting two out of only three Vizslas in the United States (Chicago Tribune, 1951; The New York Times, 1951). This was at the 11th Annual International Kennel Club's all-breed dog show in the International Amphitheater, at 42nd St. and Halsted St. in Chicago. Until the breed's recognition by the American Kennel Club in 1960, Vizslas competed in the Miscellaneous Class, and were not eligible for the Best in Show win. Instead, the registries occurred in the Field Dog Stud Book. These two Vizslas, co-owned by Mr. and Mrs. Frank Tallman and Emmett Scanlan of the American Embassy in Rome, caused "mass interest centered" on them (The New York Times, 1951, p. S4).

First Vizsla Litter Born on The U.S. Soil

March 23, 1952 marked a crucial milestone in the history of the Vizsla in the United States (The Vizsla Club of America, n.d.). The first known Vizsla litter from Sari and Rex breeding was born on that day. The photo of Rex and Sari and their first-born litter of six puppies, owned by Frank Tallman, appeared in several newsletters (Toledo Blade, May 1952; The Windsor Star, April, 1952). Mr. Tallman reported having only one adult pair of Vizslas in the country. Due to lack of pedigree documents, the owners could not register this litter. Nevertheless, these puppies became the Vizsla's foundation stock in the United States (Coffman, 1991). The Frank Tallman family kept a female puppy out of Sari and Rex's March 1952 litter and named her Duchess (The Kansas City, 1954). Duchess died in 1954 at the age of 2.5 years when run over by a speeding car in front of the Tallman's house at 3400 West Coleman Road. Prior to her death, she delivered nine puppies sired by a 7-year old Pik. (Kansas City lawyer Emmett Scanlan Jr. noted Pik, a field trial winner in Yugoslavia, and brought him from Italy where he worked with the embassy.)

On September 6, 1952, The Standard Star published a photo of three Tallman daughters, Janice, Michaela, and Clare, holding the puppies set to appear at the 33th Westchester Kennel Dog Show the next day.

Vizslas Gelse and Gemme Arrive in The U.S.

On July 2, 1951, two “cinnamon-colored” female Vizslas, Gelse and Gemme von Schloss Loosdorf, pictured arriving in Minneapolis on that day (The Minneapolis Star, 1951). John (Jack) Hatfield (a Scaffolding Salesman residing at 5018 43rd Avenue S., Minneapolis) and William Olson (78th Street & Normadale Road, Minneapolis) reported importing these 3.5-months-old puppies. The Vizsla owners claimed it was a “professional secret” on how they were able to arrange for these puppies, but shared that they first flew from Hungary to Vienna, Austria, prior to coming to the United States. They said it was a two-way smuggle and they gave two other rare breeds from the United States in exchange for these two Hungarian Vizslas (The Palm Beach, 1959, p. 27). The article referred to Olson as to a breeder of German Short-Haired Pointers, so it is possible this was at least one of the exchanged breeds. At that time, Hatfield believed there were only three other Vizslas in the United States; all three brought earlier by Mr. Tallman.

Gelse and Gemme V Schloss Loosdorf were two generations down from the Betyar and Panni XV Austrian breeding. Elizabeth M. Mihalyi, who was in charge of saving Panni XV “no matter what happened to jewels, money or possessions” (Magyar Vizsla Club of America, 1954) during her dare escape from the occupied Hungary, was unable to cross the border with her Vizsla. Though Mrs. Mihalyi had to leave Panni XV in Austria, she completed her task of saving the dog. Not only did Mrs. Mihalyi saved Panni XV, but also she arranged for her connection with Hofbauers of Vienna’s Vizsla named Betyar. Betyar, registered with the Austrian Kennel Club Vizsla, was from the Esterhazy kennels. Panni XV and Betyar produced puppies and some of their descendants eventually made their way to the United States.

In 1951, Gelse, owned by William Olson and handled by Marly Whiting, won High in Trial in Minneapolis, Minnesota, for their Novice Obedience test with the score of 199. One of Gelse V Schloss Loosdorf's puppies named Gina became the first Vizsla shown in Arizona (The Arizona Republic, 1954). This was on November 21, 1954 at Sahuaro State Kennel Club's sanctioned match show at Encanto Park. Gina's owner was Mrs. William McCauley, residing at 3127 E. Garfield, who purchased her from Mr. Olson.

Mr. P. Davis shared with a reporter that there were only five Vizslas in November 1951 and he was lucky to look after the newest imports, two 3.5-month-old female Vizslas (Island Country Times, 1951), who pointed a pheasant on the first day of training (Kesting, 1951).

First Five- and Six-Generation-Pedigreed Vizslas are in The U.S.

In 1951, Dr. Ivan Osborn, a veterinarian from Minnesota, started importing actively, bringing over 40 Vizslas during his lifetime. Among imported Vizslas were Hess V Schloss Loosdorf and Marika Dravavolgy from Betyar and Panni XV breeding, not registered due to lack of complete pedigrees. Dr. Osborn imported his first five-generation-pedigreed stud named Broc Olca from Czechoslovakia in 1953 (Coffman, 1991), marking a significant milestone in Vizsla history. In the following 1954 year, he marked another milestone when he bred Broc Olca to his female from the Povazia Czechoslovakian line, producing first puppies with six-generation pedigree (Coffman, 1991). A photo of Broc Olca on point appeared in The Los Angeles Times on November 14, 1954.

Jutka Arrives in The U.S.

Also in 1951, another Hungarian, Jeno Das, a former colonel in the Hungarian Army sponsored by the Lake Street Presbyterian Church, arrived in Hamburg, where he settled on South Park Ave near Route 20 (Buffalo Evening News, 1955). Mr. Das shared with a Buffalo Evening News reporter in May 1951 how he lived for three months "on three cups of cocoa a day" (p. 37) to save money for his old Vizsla named Jutka for her travel to the United States. He

worked with Orleman & Son piano makers, saved all the money for his dog, and planned to open a kennel on two acres of land arranged for him. Rev. Eugene F. Molnar, Minister of the Hungarian Presbyterian Church in Lackawanna shared going to the airport with Mr. Das to meet Jutka there (Buffalo Evening News, 1955). "The dog was nearly delirious with joy" to see his owner again (p. 37). Sadly, Jutka soon died. However, Mr. Das was able to get Jutka's female puppy and named her Jutka II. He later bred her to a Missouri Vizsla male. In December 1954, Jutka II delivered 11 puppies (all of them pictured in the article), each priced between 500 and 600 dollars. Jenó Dus mentioned training Darrka, Tallman's 10-month-old female Vizsla for the Retriever Dog Night event on November 1, 1955. Darrka's photo with A.J. Stephens, President of the Field and Stream Sportsmen's Conservation Club was in The Kansas City Star's October 30, 1955 issue.

First Vizsla Shows Across the Country

In 1952, Jack Hatfield and Mabel reported handling Vizslas in the show rings. Mrs. Millchip handled Tito, owned by Frank Tallman, at the International Kennel Club on March 29, 1952 (Casper Star Tribune, 1952) and Mr. Hatfield showed Gemme von Schloss Loosdorf on May 4, 1952 at the Minneapolis Kennel Club's 21st annual all-breed dog show in the Minneapolis Auditorium (Star Tribune, 1952). A rare find was a photograph of Mrs. Millchip teaching Janie, the daughter of Frank Tallman, on how to stack Rex, getting ready for the upcoming February 22, 1953 dog show (The Kansas City Star, 1953). Another rare find was a photo of Gemme von Schloss Loosdorf, free stalking in front of a four-year-old Andrea Dangerfield, a daughter of Mr. Hatfield's neighbors (Star Tribune, 1952).

The first Vizsla show in the East was on September 7, 1952 at the 35th Westchester Kennel Club dog show, according to The Record newspaper (Hover, 1952). At that time, there were believed to be 26 Vizslas in the country including ten puppies from two litters bred by Mr. Tallman. On September 17, 1952, The Kansas City Star reported the results of the Annual

Kansas Field and Gun Dog Club show with the first place won by Rex, handled by Mr. Tallman, second place going to Barj, handled by Mrs. Tallman, and third place awarded to Duchess, handled by Mr. Tallman.

In a rear photograph published on August 17, 1952 (The Kansas City Star), the author found Frank Tallman and William Olson stacking side-by-side their dogs, Rex and Gemme. The article stated Mr. Tallman owned 14 Vizslas at that time.

1953-1959

The number of Vizslas is Growing in The U.S.

Others followed the lead. Mr. Jack Ahearn, an ex-Marine and resident of Wagram originally from Massachusetts, in March 1953 shared the starting field training Vizslas in addition to Weimaraners (Brown, 1953). At the time of the article publications, he was training a female Vizsla named Trixie. He shared that the cost for a Vizsla puppy was between 700 and 800 dollars at that time and that Trixie was insured by Lloyd's of London for five thousand dollars.

In 1954, Jeno Das, who resided in Northern New York State, bred Jutka, a female from Sari and Rex's breeding, to Pik, producing Csisckas of Goncoltanya, later used in the establishing of the Hunts of Tennessee line (Coffman, 1991).

Another puppy out of Sari and Rex's breeding mentioned by the media was a male Vizsla named Prince. Prince's photo appeared in Washington Missouri on August 13, 1953 and in Independent on September 5, 1954. The August issue discussed Prince's multiple (in February, May, and August) wins in the show ring, despite him being a puppy. Henry P. Davis from Labadie, Missouri, who owned Prince, reported to reside at 1002 Walnut in Kansas City around that time.

In his interview published by Ledger-Star on May 6, 1954, Frank Tallman reported 45 members of the Magyar Vizsla Club and about 90 Vizslas in the United States registered

(Edgar, 1954, p. 41). At that time, Frank was arranging to bring more Vizslas from an Austrian breeder. The same newspaper published a photo of a nice male puppy Mark who was steady on point and mentioned a recent litter of nine puppies from his female and his Yugoslavian male Vizsla. The article also talked about Captain Victor Tate of Norfolk owning one of Frank's dogs.

A photo of Mrs. Mihalyi (described as an Omaha portrait artist residing at 100th & Pacific Street) and her two female Vizslas appeared in the Evening World – Herald on October 31, 1955. These Vizslas were a 15-month-old Panni XVI from William A. Olson of Minneapolis and a 3-month-old Anesa from Charles F. Hunt of Richton Park, Ill (p. 23). Another photo of Mrs. Mihalyi with Vizslas, captured during her stay as a houseguest at Mr. and Mrs. Elmer N. Olson, 2615 Park Avenue, appeared in Star Tribune on September 29, 1955.

The six-month-old male Vizsla named Duke showcased in the September 29, 1955 newspaper (Nelson, 1955). Dr. John J. Tilton acquired Duke from the Minneapolis man, who flew him and other three puppies from Hungary. Duke was the first Vizsla to arrive in Bellevue, Iowa, with about 20 Vizslas in total living in the United States by that time. Dr. Tilton got Duke, described as a "dark sandy yellow" colored with compact feet "like those of a cat," to hunt with him (p. 22).

Mr. Tom Pratt, a dry cleaner residing in Clarion, Iowa, shared he smuggled his female Vizsla named Tia (registered name Alma Olea) from Hungary during the revolt of 1956 (Owens, 1958). At the time of the 1958 article's publication, Mr. Pratt had in his kennels a litter of seven puppies from Tia and a Minnesota Vizsla, as well as six five-month-old puppies owned by F. A. Rummel, a Britt banker. Around that time, about 187 Vizslas were part of the Vizsla Club of America.

A photo of a boy Garry Carpenter and a ten-month-old Vizsla appeared in Oakland Tribune on March 2, 1956. The Vizsla was to appear on March 10 and 11 at the Oakland Kennel Club show.

A reporter, in April 15, 1956 *The News and Observer*, issued an apology to a local Vizsla's owners for dismissing the dog previously because of her name's difficult pronunciation. A reader, Eula Greenwood called the reporter back to educate about the breed qualities and history. It turned out that the Vizsla named Gyongyver von Kotpussta and owned by John Fegarassy-Wallner earned awards at the most recent show.

The first Vizsla in Kentucky and South was Kheta (Kheta-Ke-Kolocsa) shown on March 18, 1956 at the Mid-Kentucky Kennel Club show in Hodgenville. The owners of this 17-month-old female Vizsla, stacked for a photo, were Sgt. R.G. Short and Mrs. Short, Vine Grove, Kentucky (*The Courier Journal*, 1956).

A Vizsla named Gina von Zisko, owned by E.L. Keesee of Santa Ana, pictured with the owners' five-year-old daughter Marianna Keesee in the June 21, 1956 issue of *The Los Angeles Times*. Gina prepared for the 21st Annual Long Beach Show at Veterans Memorial Stadium in the upcoming weekend.

Mr. Hatfield' Weimaraner and Vizsla females who had puppies at the same time appeared in the December 3, 1956 issue of *The Minneapolis*. Both females shared 16 puppies (11 Vizslas and 5 Weimaraners) and did not mind helping one another feeding them all. Later in the same month, this newspaper published another photo and covered another story about Mr. Hatfield giving Judith and Susan Gyorky, two Hungarian refugee girls, a puppy from his recent litter of nine puppies (*The Minneapolis Star*, 1956, December 20). At that time, Mr. Hatfield's kennel was at 806 Pelham Boulevard, St. Paul.

In 1957, the newspapers continued to report Vizsla as a rare breed (Hager, 1957). A photo of a Vizsla, owned by Morris Chatfield, a breeder and trainer residing at 7700 W. Lake Street, St. Louis, appeared in *Star Tribune* as one of the rare dogs to compete in the 27th Annual Minneapolis Kennel Club Show (Hager, 1957).

In 1957, The Ogden Standard ran a story about the only Vizsla in Utah. The newspaper published a photo of a Vizsla named a-Von-Schloss-Loosdorf stacked by Lynn Merrill, 1662 24th St. Mr. Merrill acquired this dog from Mr. Olson.

On August 7, 1957, Reading Eagle announced the birth of the Vizsla litter owned by Mr. and Mrs. Elroy P. Master in Berks County. In the photo, the family's children William and Elsa play with seven puppies with "a short and dense coat of rather dark, sandy yellow hair" on the family's Berks Veldt Farm. This litter was reported as the first born in Berks County.

A nine-month-old Vizsla owned by Mr. and Mrs. Bud Lucas of Klamath Falls and handled by Kathy McDonald at the 31st Klamath Dog Fanciers' Show appeared in the August 25, 1957 issue of Herald and News.

A photo of Chinook Olca Povagla, a two-year-old Vizsla owned by Anne Chelini appeared in the November 17, 1957 issue of The San Francisco Examiner (Gordon, 1957). accompanied some insights into the breed history and shared that the Vizsla performs the best when it is able to stay close to their family, inside their homes and not in a kennel.

A Vizsla named Diana-Olca, pictured with her seven puppies in the February 16, 1958 issue of Independent Sun, travelled on Alexa von Manner's visa back and forth between Austria and North America (Price, 1958). Diana Olca's son Ciro, owned by Joe Benastar of Marysville reported placing in a group in a Seattle show, and her entire litter of six puppies went to Charles Hunt, Richton Park, Illinois.

The first two Vizslas in Georgia reported in 1958 were a male Vizsla named Snooper (Brok von Dravavology), owned by Mr. and Mrs. Cecil E. Clapp of 241 Maxwell St. in Decatur and a female Vizsla owned by C.E. Tolbert of Whitesburg (Woodward, 1958). Snooper appears in a photograph with Becky Clapp, the family's daughter.

Baron (Baron Rex Selle), a two-year-old male Vizsla, appeared in a photo with his owner Leo F. Turcotte of 76 Pitroff Ave., South Hadley (The Holyoke Daily, 1958). Mr. Turcotte proudly

shared his registration number, 160, with the Vizsla Club of America. Baron came from a kennel in Missouri and he was a grandson of a prize-winning Vizsla owned by Marshall Tito in Yugoslavia.

A Vizsla named Ancia, owned by O.W. Whitehead, 1325 Norwood Drive SE, appeared on a photo with the family's daughter, a nine-year-old Sally. The photo, taken in Cedar Rapids, in Iowa, found published in *The Gazette* (1958).

Mr. Olson was not the only breeder of German Short-Haired Pointers who decided to breed Vizslas. The *Lincoln Star* on July 24, 1958 ran a story about Mr. and Mrs. Richard Armstrong of 1224 Adams, who decided to do the same (Hasselbalch, 1958). They named their first Vizsla Goldie's Rust.

Another first reported in the press was on November 9, 1958, this time it was a Vizsla litter born in Nebraska. Maggie, a female "rust-gold-colored" Vizsla with six-generation pedigree and owned by Maurice Graff of Seward, delivered eight puppies (*Omaha World*, 1958, 3C). The breeding sire was Brock, owned by Dr. Osborn of LeSueur, Minnesota.

Another rare find was a photo of a female Vizsla named Zoz (Pallas Povazia) sitting beside a two-year old Michelle Price, who was playing with her two puppies (Mohn, 1958). The child was the daughter of Mr. John Price, who was residing at the southeast corner of Chestnut and Elm Sta.

Vizslas Are Not Ordinary Pets

Unique photos of Ms. Joan Fish, a British Consul covering Utah, Wyoming and Colorado with headquarters in Denver, pictured with her Vizsla named Csisckas and pronounced Chekos during her November 1958 pheasant hunt (*The Ogden Standard Examiner*, 1958; *The Salt Lake Tribune*, 1958). Ms. Fish joined Dr. Frank B. Schick from the University of Utah's Political Science Department, Einar Larsen, President of the Corinne Posted Hunting Area, Ruggles Porter, Conservation Officer, and Miles Ferry, Secretary for this hunting experience in Corinne.

Ms. Fish was in Budapest when the Hungarian revolt occurred, pulled some strings, and paid 500 cigarettes for this Vizsla and another dog, who escaped Hungary with her. According to this article, Queen Elizabeth of England cited this dog for life saving. The Vizsla proved to be a great hunter and the hunters bagged their daily limit.

A photo of a happy male Vizsla named Kish appeared in the July 12, 1959 Ohio newspaper Toledo Sunday Blade. He posed on a couch with a young girl named Beverley and the family's cat Squeekie. Mrs. Charles Wolcott, who resided at her Islington Street home in Toledo, owned Kish or Kisfiam (meaning a small loved boy), described as weighing about 70 pounds and standing 25 inches with a "sleek cinnamon coat" who loved to help Wolcotts carrying bags and other things to their places at home (p. 7). At that time, he was the only known Vizsla in Toledo, who was, according to the owner, a grandson of a Vizsla that came to America with "a woman who escaped from Hungary with nothing but a satchel and her two dogs" (p. 7). The owners told a reporter that Kish knew when it was time to eat. When he heard the cathedral bells, Kish took a can of food from a kitchen or basement and brought it to his owners. If nobody was home, he opened the can with his teeth (p. 7). The same article pictured a photo of a male puppy Vizsla named Danny, son of Vanda Olca; both dogs owned by Gilbert H. Wildman from Vero Beach.

On December 31, 1956, The Washington Post shared a conversational piece at Rear Adm. And Mrs. William J. Marshall's where a reporter learned about the admiral's Vizsla story. The Vizsla's name was Kimbasan (translated from Japanese as Mr. Gold Tooth) (p. B3). The puppy had a disorder resulting in soft teeth and making him unable to chew bones. Marshalls found a solution and "capped [his teeth] with gold" (B3).

A remarkable story of Piccolo, a 3.5-year-old Vizsla, owned by Mrs. Aileen Quirk of 4953 Forest Avenue, highlighted the unique qualities of the breed in a story run by The Kansas City Star on July 9, 1958. A photo of a "lap dog," wishing to spend every minute of his life with his

favorite person, accompanied the story (p. 1). When in June 1958, Mrs. Quirk took him to a dog kennel so she could travel for a week to attend a work-related (she worked at Aileen Quirk & Sons) bean convention in Colorado Springs, he first run after her car and jumped to its back seat. After his return to the kennel, he went on a hunger strike, and a week later, he used his mouth to chew the wood and wire fencing and his smarts to open the gates, and escaped. It took Piccolo 30 hours to cover 22 miles and find his way back home. It turned out Mrs. Quirk got Piccolo three years ago from his former owner, who was displeased with the dog's desire to sleep on the top of his Cadillac. Since when home alone, Piccolo finds the way to open the door handles and create mischief, Mrs. Quirk takes him to work. This is what Piccolo enjoyed the most, being part of his owner's life, every minute of it.

Vizslas Gaining Popularity in the Field in The U.S.

Vizslas participated in the simulated field trials on the second floor of the Amphitheater during the show in March 1952, to demonstrate "these magnificent gun dogs in action" (Joiner, 1952, p. 3).

The Kansas City Star report on May 1, 1955 praised Vizsla's performance in the gun dog stakes. Mike Von Loosdorf, a 16-month-old Vizsla owned and handled by Harry Holt, demonstrated "a perfect point, one beautiful back and three retrieves to his credit" (p. 6B).

Nikki of Bayview, owned by George Yamamote of Bayview Greenhouses, Gorst, found surrounded by her puppy and derby stakes national win trophies and spotlighted in the May 25, 1956 issue of Bremerton Sun. According to the May 14 issue of Bremerton Sun, Nikki won over other dogs trained and handled by Robert S. Foster, including Rakk owned by Dr. Osborn. Foster reported as a houseguest to Dr. Osborn at that time. More about Yamamotes and their "golden-colored hunting dogs" (p. 16) found in the May 18, 1955 issue of the same named newspaper. Mr. Yamamoto was a native of Seattle and served in the U.S. Army in World War II. On a photo, three of his daughters pictured with 4-month-old puppies Nikki of Bayview (their

new puppy) and Tor of Shirbobs (Mr. Robert Forrest's puppy), which recently arrived from Le Sueur, Minnesota. By that time, there were only 4-5 Vizslas on the West coast.

One of the top field trainers of Vizslas, Clarence (Knut) Nelson of Stoddard, who trained a Vizsla named Freckles owned by Judge and Mrs. Rudolph Desort of Palatine, Illinois, talked about a Vizsla named Freckles (The La Crosse Tribune, 1956). Freckles' exceptional performance, noted at the National Vizsla Trial at St. Paul earlier in the same year, prompted Charles Hunt to seek wider distribution of written by Nelson articles on training gun dogs.

On May 12, 1957, Kansas citizens had an opportunity to watch 20 Vizslas - from Illinois, Minnesota, Missouri, and Texas - competing in a field trial at the Marygle Farm on Highway 150 (The Kansas City, 1957).

In March 1957, the Evansville Press covered the exceptional field qualities of Dr. Osborn's Rakkelle, who while handled by Paul Saho of Champaign, Illinois, captured second place in the shooting dog stakes (Hill, 1957). Rakkelle, who had a 12-generation pedigree, by 33 months was placed in nine shooting dog stakes.

Mr. Roy Geil of Kingston, Washington - who was a brother Mrs. Maud Lortin Myers, publisher of the Tulsa World - talked about his 14-month-old female Vizsla named Sue C Sabe Lidi, who won many field trophies across the Northwestern part of the United States, a story run by Tulsa Daily World on October 9, 1958 (Ferguson, 1958).

The national all age champion, a two-year old Vizsla named Nikki's Arco of Shirbob, owned and handled by Bob Foster at 142 Lafayette Avenue, was pictured with multiple trophies on September 14, 1959. The Vizsla and owner were getting ready to compete at Fort Lewis next weekend. Earlier, in October 1958, Nikki's photo on point at 15-months age appeared in the Bremerton Sun. Nikki started competing in trials since he was a puppy, at seven-months age, always winning a prize.

Breed Recognition by the American Kennel Club

In 1959, the newspapers talked about the Vizsla breed to earn the registered status with the American Kennel Club (Carnes, 1959). By 1960, there were about 400 three-generation Vizslas registered in the United States leading to the breed's official recognition by the American Kennel Club that year.

Vizsla Versatility in The U.S. Press

The Vizsla's qualities covered in newspapers extended beyond work in the field and show ring. They were portrayed as family members and helpful in giving a hand in unique situations. For example, the October 20, 1958 Buffalo Evening News published a photo of a Vizsla named Chardarsh holding a bottle of milk for a two-week-old fawn who was drinking it. Chardash lived at the Birch Hill game park near Brewster, New York. Another photo of Chardash holding in his teeth a plate with a cup while an eight-year-old Diane Duprey pouring milk into the cup (Daily News, 1958, p. 22).

For some time, Mr. Hatfield advocated for the "bloodhound network" to have dogs searching for missing people and crime suspects (Star Tribune, October 1952; McDonald, 1953). Star Tribune published a photo of his two-year old Vizsla's with Tom Jones, Minneapolis Police Chief taken during conversations about the network (October 1952). William Olson and Jack Hatfield and Olson's Vizsla became part of a missing person October 1954 search, which became one of the top stories of that year and the following years (Olson, 1954). On October 17, the four-year child named LaVern Enget went missing from his farm in the Northeast of Powers Lake, North Dakota. Thousands of volunteers searched the area for a few months with ten dogs and their handlers joining the search on the 8th day, after the snowfall. At that time, Mr. Olson believed that the dogs "were called too late" and though "the dogs had found several footprints," the melting snow covered the scent (p.3). (The child's body was found only a year and 13 days later, he had drowned in a slough a mile away from home.)

Conclusions

Despite most of the reviewed evidence pointing to Frank Tallman being the first to bring a Vizsla to the United States, there are a few references (King, 1959; Coffman, 1991) suggesting there were earlier Vizsla arrivals.

The author of this article enjoyed researching the subject of the first Vizslas of the United States and thrilled finding the evidence of earlier than previously thought presence of this exceptional breed in the country. These findings are not to undermine the great contributions of Frank Tallman, William Olson, Jack Hatfield, Ivan Osborn, Jeno Dus, and many others who devoted their lives to establishing the Vizsla breed in the United States, by showing, trialing, and breeding their dogs, and organizing and running the Vizsla Clubs. Because of the exceptional contributions and sacrifices made by these individuals and their families, the Vizsla breed not only survived, it has blossomed and became recognized by the American Kennel Club.

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